

PERIODIC ACID AND PERIODATES. PART I. SOLUBILITY OF PERIODIC ACID IN WATER

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The solubility of periodic acid in water at temperatures between 0° and 45° has been determined. The heat of solution of the acid in a saturated solution has been calculated from these data. It is found that the process is endothermic, the thermal change being small and about of the same order as observed in mixing acetic acid with small quantities of water in a calorimeter. There is some indication that the acid may exist in two forms differing in water content, the probable transition temperature being 29.5°.

Practically no quantitative data for the solubility of periodic acid have appeared in literature. According to Langlois (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1852, **34**, 257) periodic acid is slightly soluble in alcohol, less soluble in ether, and very soluble in water. Hill (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 2678) has mentioned that the solubility of periodic acid at room temperature is about 53%. This figure was obtained after analysing the mother-liquor after the crystallisation of periodic acid, and therefore it may be only approximate. Moreover, the temperature is not defined precisely. Willard ("Inorganic Synthesis", Vol. I, p. 173, McGraw Hill Book Co., London, 1939) gives the following figures (Table I) for the solubility of periodic acid in concentrated nitric acid of sp. gr. 1.42.

TABLE I

Temperature.	H ₅ IO ₆ (g./100 c.c.)	H ₅ IO ₆ (g. per 100 g. soln.)
-12±1°	5.88	3.95
26±0.05°	7.82	5.41

He further mentions that the solubility rises rapidly above 25° and is about ten times as much in water as in concentrated nitric acid. It is therefore clear that no systematic attempt at measuring the solubility of periodic acid in water at different temperatures has been made. Nevertheless, such a study might be valuable in deciding whether or not different periodic acids exist in contact with their saturated solutions at different temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The periodic acid was prepared by oxidation of sodium iodate in solution by potassium persulphate, as described by Booth ("Inorganic Synthesis", Vol. I, p. 168).

Two different methods were employed to estimate the periodic acid. The first, due to Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1086) depends on the liberation of iodine from potassium iodide under specified conditions. The second, due to Müller and Friedberger (*Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 2665), also makes use of the same reaction but under different conditions; under these conditions iodic acid and iodates do not liberate iodine. The two methods were found to check each other closely.

The experimental arrangement for the determination of solubility consisted of a small bulb of about 10c.c. capacity blown out of pyrex glass tubing. A little water and excess of periodic acid were introduced into it and the stem of the bulb was sealed off. It was then immersed in a water thermostat and shaken mechanically. Shaking was stopped after 48 hours and the tube was allowed to stand another 24 hours for the solid to settle down. The clear solution was then taken out and analysed. Solubility measurements at various temperatures were made. The thermostat used for all the temperatures, except 0° and 20°, was an ordinary electrically maintained one with a maximum temperature variation of 0.05°. For 0°, the self-explanatory arrangement shown in Fig. 1 was used. By this arrangement the temperature could be maintained at 0° for about 3 days with a single charge of ice during winter. The water inside the cylinder showed a maximum variation in temperature of 0.2°. For a temperature of 20°, the same arrangement was used, but instead of taking ice in the Dewar vessel water at 20° was taken. By adding a few pieces of ice occasionally the temperature could be maintained at 20°.

FIG. 1.

TABLE II

Temp. ..	0°	20°	25°	33°	35°	37°	40°	45°
Acid, HIO_4 , $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ contain- ed in 100 g. of sat. soln in g. . .	77.91	78.57	78.74	79.32	79.50	79.66	80.30	80.78

FIG. 2

DISCUSSION

The results obtained from these measurements are recorded in Table II. The data are shown graphically in Fig. 2 in which the solubility has been plotted against the corresponding temperature. The experimental points are found to lie on two distinct lines AP and BP which are almost straight and intersect at the point P. This point corresponds to a temperature of about 29.5°. Below this temperature the solubility increases at the rate of about 0.03 g. per degree; above P it increases at the rate of about 0.12 g. per degree, that is to say, about four-fold as rapidly.

These facts lend support to the possibility that AP and BP may be the solubility curves of two different forms of the acid, probably differing in water content. P should then be the transition point for the two forms. Incidentally, the present experiments support the previously recorded qualitative fact that the solubility of periodic acid increases rapidly above 25°.

FIG. 3

It is possible to calculate with the help of the present data the approximate heats of solution of the two forms. For this purpose the equation

$$\ln \frac{S_2}{S_1} = \frac{\mathcal{L}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right)$$

may be used. Here S_1 , S_2 are the solubilities of the substance at the absolute temperatures T_1 , T_2 respectively and \mathcal{L} is the calorimetric heat of solution in a saturated solution (cf. Partington, "Thermodynamics", p. 305, London, 1913). Although this equation is not universally accepted (*Brit. Chem. Abs.*, 1888, ii, 552; 1899, ii, 11,545) it has been frequently used to calculate \mathcal{L} from observed solubilities at different temperatures. Obviously, average values of \mathcal{L}/R may be obtained by plotting the logarithm of solubility against the inverse of the absolute temperature and measuring the slopes of the resulting curves. This has been shown in Fig. 3. It is found that the graphs are practically straight lines showing that there is no sensible variation in the value of \mathcal{L} for each form in the range of measurements. The values of \mathcal{L} have been calculated from these slopes and come out to be about 69 and 298 cal. per mole respectively for the two forms below and above 29.5°. These values may be compared with 6857 cal. for succinic acid—water at 5° and 6500 cal. for *o*-nitrobenzoic acid—water at 20°. Potassium perchlorate has a heat of solution of 12300 cal. (Noyes and Sammet, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 43, 513). Obviously the heat of solution of periodic acid is small in comparison with these values although heat is absorbed in each case. It may probably be compared to the heat of solution of acetic acid in water studied by Thomsen; in these measurements the acid was mixed with different proportions of water and the heat evolved measured in a calorimeter. Thomsen found that one mole of the acid mixed with half a mole of water brought about an absorption of 130 cal. of heat (Landolt-Börnstein's Tables, p. 885, Berlin, 1912), but he did not appear to have studied the thermal effect at differ-

ent temperatures. He, however, obtained much variation in the measured heat as the proportion of water was increased, the process of solution becoming exothermic at 20 moles of water and above. The heat of solution with different proportions of water at a constant temperature therefore deserves investigation in the case of periodic acid also, and is proposed to be taken up later.

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